

Viscosity of Liquids

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Based on Telang's calculations¹, Palit² deduced the following expression for the viscosity of liquids, interrelating the viscosity, surface tension, and density of liquids at constant temperature :

$$\log_{10} (\eta M) = \frac{zN^{1/3}}{2.303R} \cdot \frac{\gamma (M/\rho)^{2/3}}{T} + \Phi (1/\rho)$$

where $z = 1.091^3$ for cubical packing, $N =$ Avogadro's number, $\Phi (1/\rho) =$ a function of specific volume, and all the other quantities have their usual significance. Palit² has suggested that since the variation of specific volume is very small along a homologous series, $\Phi (1/\rho)$ can be regarded as a constant at constant temperature for a homologous series. Owing to the unavailability of relevant data for diverse types of liquids, the above expression was examined with regard to its various implications for the alkanes only.

Recently published data on viscosity, surface tension, and density of CCl_4 and SnCl_4 by Pugachevich *et al*³ have led to another aspect of the above expression being examined. Taking the variation of $\Phi(1/\rho)$ with temperature to be very small, the plot of $\log_{10} (\eta M)$ against $\gamma (M/\rho)^{2/3}/T$ should be linear according to the above equation, with a constant slope of 0.481 for all liquids having cubical packing. Fig. 1 shows this to be more or less true for the three liquids studied. From Table I the following points may be noted.

FIG. 1

1. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1949, 17, 556.
2. *This Journal*, 1963, 40, 721.
3. *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 8, 406.

(i) The slopes for the three liquids have the same order as the calculated value. Any deviation in magnitude from the calculated value may be ascribed to the probable variation of z with temperature and /or departure of z from the assumed value of 1.091 due to distortion of spherical shape and cubical packing of molecules.

(ii) The intercepts for all the three liquids are negative², the value depending on the density of the given liquids.

TABLE I

Liquid	Slope		*Intercept [= Φ (1/ ρ)]
	*Obs.	Calc. ($z \times 1.091$)	
C ₁₁ H ₂₄	0.369	0.481	-0.859
SnCl ₄	0.303		-0.337
CCl ₄	0.407		-0.618

* Obtained by the method of least squares.